

Jahn-Teller Couplings and Exciton Models Reveal Origins of Chiroptical Activity in Symmetric Cyclic π -Conjugated Systems

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Abstract

Understanding the origin of chiroptical responses in symmetric cyclic π -conjugated systems is key to advancing their application in optoelectronic and spintronic technologies. Here we document that such response is intrinsically nonadiabatic and it arises from the entangled contributions of electronic states and molecular vibrations. We exploit a comprehensive theoretical framework that unifies localized exciton coupling and delocalized Jahn-Teller (JT) vibronic models, two traditionally distinct approaches, to accurately predict the ECD spectra of chiral spirobifluorene macrocycles. We show that using a flexible method to parameterize linear vibronic coupling (LVC) models in both localized and delocalized representations enables direct comparison of excitonic and non-adiabatic effects. We demonstrate that quantum dynamical simulations on both models reproduce the experimental ECD spectrum of a D_3 -symmetric macrocycle (P,P,P)-**1** with high accuracy and reveal that the coupling between nuclear and electronic motions plays a dominant role in shaping its chiroptical response. This analysis highlights the critical influence of conical intersections, exciton-charge transfer interactions, and symmetry-guided combinations of local transition dipoles. Importantly, the same approach captures the spectral features of a less symmetric C_2 stereoisomer (P,P,M)-**1**, underscoring the generality

of the method. This dual-framework strategy provides deep mechanistic insight into the interplay of symmetry, vibronic coupling, and excitonic interactions, and offers a powerful design tool for next-generation chiral materials

1 Introduction

Twisted molecular systems have attracted the interest of researchers due to both their aesthetic appeal and possibility for implementation in optoelectronic applications such as optical displays, biosensing, and spintronics.¹⁻⁶ Discrete symmetric systems presenting a cyclic arrangement of identical chromophores are synthetically accessible and an ideal playground to gain fundamental understanding in structure-properties relationship. A judicious choice of the nature of the constituting moieties enables access to chiroptical systems with unique geometry and optoelectronic properties. Conjugated fragments such as binaphthyls,⁷ helicenes,⁸ polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons,⁹ spirobifluorenes (SBFs),⁷ are often employed with the aim to provide intense optoelectronic responses. Particularly, we have shown the suitability of axially chiral SBFs for the development of diverse macrocycles presenting remarkable chiroptical responses.^{10,11} It is easy to realize that the chiroptical properties of these systems have intrinsically a non-adiabatic origin. This fact can be understood both within a localized or a de-localized picture. The synthetic route adopted to prepare these systems is naturally allied to an interpretation of their chiroptical properties according to a localized exciton-like picture, i.e. thinking that each unit contributes with a local excitation and their coupling determines the chiroptical response.^{12,13} The specificity of these systems however is that, due to the covalent bonds and the small distance in space, interactions between local states are expected to be too strong to be described by standard excitonic models and, therefore, more suitable approaches are required.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ A completely different point of view in terms of delocalized states, i.e of the full macrocycle, interacting through Conical Intersections (CoIs), is indeed possible at least when these molecular units form closed cyclic structures. In fact, C_n and D_n symmetric systems with $n \geq 3$ present degenerate excited states, and symmetry-imposed CoIs which trigger Jahn-Teller (JT) and/or pseudo- Jahn-Teller (pJT) non-adiabatic effects.¹⁷

Traditionally the effects of excitonic interactions and CoIs have been addressed resorting to different families of theoretical models. However, the above considerations strongly suggest that for chiral cyclic structures made up of repetitive units, switching between the two alternative pictures should be possible, potentially allowing for a new and more in-depth understanding of the properties of these interesting compounds. In this contribution we show that such a dual description is made accessible by adopting generalized nonadiabatic linear vibronic coupling (LVC) models^{18,19} and flexible diabaticization techniques that can al-

ternatively use as reference states either delocalized or localized states, the latter ones defined for suitable molecular fragments.^{20,21} In these models the optical response is computed through the quantum dynamical evolution of wavepackets running on the coupled electronic states, an inherently nonadiabatic process. Particularly, we focus on trigonal diethynylspirobifluorene (DES) macrocycle (P,P,P)-**1** (where (P,P,P) denotes the stereogenic descriptors of the three chiral axes present in molecule **1**, in Figure 1a) with D_3 symmetry, which can be affected by JT couplings. We show that JT and pJT couplings actually dominate the electronic circular dichroism (ECD) of (P,P,P)-**1**. However, adopting a localized excitonic picture provides a qualitatively equivalent description of the ECD response, allowing us to explicitly inquire the role of exciton-exciton and exciton-charge transfer couplings (Figure 1). We also show that once the relevance of nonadiabatic interactions is unveiled in (P,P,P)-**1**, it is easy to recognize that they dominate also the chiroptical response of the stereoisomer (P,P,M)-**1** (C_2 point group, whose structure is reported in Figure S20 of the SI and differs from (P,P,P)-**1** for a change of helicity from P to M at one chiral axis), where they are not enforced by symmetry, but still existent, as expected in a localized excitonic-picture, due to the similar interactions between the three SBF units.

2 Theory

2.1 Vibronic Model Hamiltonian

We consider a LVC model^{18,19} for a set of coupled electronic diabatic states d_i written in the framework of the ground state dimensionless normal coordinates \mathbf{q} and associated momenta \mathbf{p} . The LVC Hamiltonian is the following:

$$\mathbf{H} = \sum_{\eta} \left(K + V_{\eta\eta}^{dia}(\mathbf{q}) \right) |d_{\eta}\rangle \langle d_{\eta}| + \sum_{\eta, \zeta > \eta} V_{\eta\zeta}^{dia}(\mathbf{q}) \left(|d_{\eta}\rangle \langle d_{\zeta}| + |d_{\zeta}\rangle \langle d_{\eta}| \right) \quad (1)$$

The kinetic (K) and potential (V) energy terms are

$$K = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{p}^T \mathbf{\Omega} \mathbf{p} \quad (2)$$

$$V_{\eta\eta}^{dia}(\mathbf{q}) = E_{\eta}^0 + \boldsymbol{\lambda}_{\eta\eta}^T \mathbf{q} + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{\Omega} \mathbf{q} \quad (3)$$

$$V_{\eta\zeta}^{dia}(\mathbf{q}) = E_{\eta\zeta}^0 + \boldsymbol{\lambda}_{\eta\zeta}^T \mathbf{q} \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{\Omega}$ is the diagonal matrix of the vibrational frequencies of the ground state g , E_{η}^0 represents the η -th

Figure 1: a) Chemical structure of (P,P,P) -1 showing the symmetry axes. Monomers linked by spiro carbons are represented in different colors; black, red, and blue. b) Electronic transitions S_1 , S_2 , and S_3 (top) and normal modes 337, 338, and 339 (bottom) are schematically represented. c) 2D Diabatic PES (the corresponding contour lines are in e) panel) for local excitation states on the three monomers of (P,P,P) -1 along the degenerate pair e of modes 337 (qea) and 338 (qeb) (their mathematical expression is given by the diagonal elements of Eq.5) All other modes are frozen at their values at the ground-state equilibrium geometry. Notice that the minima of the three surfaces are degenerate. d) 2D Adiabatic PES (the contour lines of the lowest surface are in f) panel) for (P,P,P) -1 along the same coordinates as in panel c), obtained by diagonalizing the LVC Hamiltonian in Eq.9). S_1 : blue surface, S_2 : cyan surface, S_3 : copper surface. Notice that S_1 and S_2 feature three equivalent minima. Parameters adopted for the plots in panels c) and d) $E_0 = 3.69$ eV, $\beta = -0.05$ eV, $\Omega = 2401$ cm^{-1} , $\lambda = 0.32$ eV (check Section 3.2 of the Supporting Information for further details). Additional representations of the contour plots of the adiabatic PES are reported in Section 3.3 of the SI middle like 337 & 338

excited-state energy at the g equilibrium geometry, $\lambda_{\eta\eta}$ is the energy gradient of state η and $\lambda_{\eta\zeta}$ is the gradient of the inter-state coupling $V_{\eta\zeta}^{dia}(\mathbf{q})$.²² Diabatic states are built by a maximum-overlap diabatization technique that requires them to be as similar as possible to some reference states. In a standard LVC (St-LVC), reference states are taken identical to the adiabatic states of the system at a reference geometry,²⁰ whereas in a Fragment diabatic LVC (FrD-LVC), such states are defined after decomposing the systems in fragments²¹ which, in our specific case, are the repetitive units of the cyclic structure depicted in black, blue, and red in Figure 1. Both in St-LVC and in FrD-LVC the parameters $\lambda_{\eta\eta}$ and $\lambda_{\eta\zeta}$ can be straightforwardly calculated by displacing the molecular structure along each normal mode, computing at each of them the diabatic Hamiltonian and taking the numerical derivatives of its terms.²¹

More schematically we considered two independent approaches.

1. **Delocalized picture with a St-LVC Hamiltonian.** We take the diabatic states to be identical to the adiabatic states of the macrocycle (P,P,P) -1 at the ground-state equilibrium geometry. In this approach, the molecular orbitals involved in the electronic transitions are delocalized over several monomers. (P,P,P) -1 diabatic states therefore belong to the D_3 point group and in particular are made equal to the three lowest excited states of the molecule the first one belonging to A_2 symmetry and the other two forming a degenerate E pair. It is the most natural basis set to describe JT and pseudo-JT effects (these results are shown in Sections 4 and 5).²³
2. **Localized picture with a FrD-LVC Hamiltonian.** In this case the diabatic states are built from orbital excitation between localized HOMO and LUMO orbitals on each single unit. Therefore they comprise both local excitations (LE) if the hole and particle orbitals belong to the same monomer or charge-transfer (CT) states if they are on different monomers. These results are shown in Section 6.

2.2 A simple reference idealized 3D model. From localized to delocalized

To facilitate the analysis of the results presented in the following sections it is helpful considering a simple localized, exciton-like model, whose basic idea is inspired to the seminal work of Gouterman and co.,²⁴ made up of three locally excited states L_1 , L_2 , L_3 (located, in our case, on the three branches of the macrocycle) with vertical excitation energy E_0 and excitonic coupling β (considered independent of the nuclear coordinates). Notice that the three vertical excitation energies are trivially equal by symmetry and the same is true for the exciton couplings due to the cyclic structure of the molecule (each molecular branch has two equivalent neighbors). Each excited state L_1 , L_2 , L_3 will have in general an equilibrium geometry different from the ground state and we can define a vibrational mode (q_1, q_2, q_3) that connects the two minima. Each of these modes will involve only the molecular branch on which the excited state is located

and therefore they will be independent (each local state is displaced along only one of the three coordinates). We invoke harmonic approximation and, in the spirit of LVC models, we assume harmonic frequencies are the same for all electronic states. By symmetry the frequency of q_1, q_2, q_3 is expected to be the same, Ω . The displacement of the equilibrium position of L_1, L_2, L_3 is then represented by a gradient λ (equal by symmetry) along the corresponding q_1, q_2, q_3 mode. With these settings, the potential energy matrix reads

$$\mathbf{H}_{dia}^{vib,loc} = A_{loc}\mathbf{I} + \begin{pmatrix} E_0 + \lambda q_1 & \beta & \beta \\ \beta & E_0 + \lambda q_2 & \beta \\ \beta & \beta & E_0 + \lambda q_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where $A_{loc} = \frac{\Omega^2}{2}(q_1^2 + q_2^2 + q_3^2)$ and \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix. $\mathbf{H}_{dia}^{vib,loc}$ is in the form of a FrD-LVC Hamiltonian (assuming the exciton couplings do not depend on the intramolecular coordinates). We can diagonalize the potential energy matrix at the reference geometry $\mathbf{0}$ characterized by $q_1 = q_2 = q_3 = 0$, $\mathbf{H}_{dia}^{vib,loc}(\mathbf{0})$, by simply defining delocalized symmetry-adapted combinations of the local states with respect to the C_3 axis of symmetry, using the transformation

$$\mathbf{T} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \\ -\frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} & \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_{dia}^{vib,del}(\mathbf{0}) = \mathbf{T}^T \begin{pmatrix} E_0 & \beta & \beta \\ \beta & E_0 & \beta \\ \beta & \beta & E_0 \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{T} = \begin{pmatrix} E_0 + 2\beta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & E_0 - \beta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & E_0 - \beta \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

we get a total symmetric state with energy $E_0 + 2\beta$ and a pair of degenerate states with energy $E_0 - \beta$. The same transformation \mathbf{T} can also be used to introduce symmetry-adapted combinations of the vibrational coordinates

$$\begin{pmatrix} q_a \\ q_{e_a} \\ q_{e_b} \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{T} \begin{pmatrix} q_1 \\ q_2 \\ q_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \\ -\frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} & \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} q_1 \\ q_2 \\ q_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

getting in an analogous way a total symmetric mode of symmetry a and a pair of degenerate vibrations that we name q_{e_a} and q_{e_b} . It is worthy to notice that the states that diagonalize $\mathbf{H}_{dia}^{vib,loc}(\mathbf{0})$ are combinations with fixed coefficients of diabatic local states therefore they are still diabatic states, but they are identical to the adiabatic states at the reference geometry; therefore we can label them as S_1, S_2 and S_3 . Transforming

the coordinate-dependent potential matrix $\mathbf{H}_{dia}^{vib,loc}$ in this new set of states, by applying the transformation \mathbf{T} , and using the symmetry adapted coordinates, we obtain the potential energy matrix

$$\mathbf{H}_{dia}^{vib,del} = A_{del}\mathbf{I} + \begin{pmatrix} E_0 + 2\beta + \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{3}}q_a & -\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{3}}q_{e_a} & -\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{3}}q_{e_b} \\ -\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{3}}q_{e_a} & E_0 - \beta + \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{3}}q_a - \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{6}}q_{e_b} & -\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{6}}q_{e_b} \\ -\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{3}}q_{e_b} & -\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{6}}q_{e_b} & E_0 - \beta + \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{3}}q_a + \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{6}}q_{e_a} \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where $A_{del} = \frac{\Omega^2}{2}(q_a^2 + q_{e_a}^2 + q_{e_b}^2)$. The new potential energy matrix $\mathbf{H}_{dia}^{vib,del}$ is in the form expected for a St-LVC Hamiltonian and, in particular, is identical to the one describing a linear JT+ pJT effect, nicely described theoretically in seminal papers to which this work is indebted, ^{19,24,25} and studied for the propyne radical cation in recent literature. ²⁶ Therefore the two adiabatic PES degenerate in D_3 symmetry exhibit a conical intersection. ¹⁹ The adiabatic PES (obtained by the diagonalization of the potential energy matrix in Eq.9) and diabatic, local PES (described by the diagonal elements of Eq.5) as a function of the pair of degenerate modes q_{e_a} and q_{e_b} , are plotted respectively in panels *d*) and *c*) of Figure 1.

This simple model, derived in deeper detail in Section 1 of the Supporting Information, suggests that the values of the parameters of the St-LVC and FrD-LVC Hamiltonians should show some relation and, ideally, the values of the couplings and gradients along modes of the macrocycle in the former one should all depend on the corresponding values of λ , the gradient of the local modes in the local basis set.

3 Computational Details

All electronic calculations were performed with DFT and TD-DFT at the CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level in gas phase as implemented in Gaussian16. ²⁷ St-LVC and FrD-LVC Hamiltonians were parameterized with diabaticization techniques according to a maximum-overlap approach, with the freely distributed Overdia 1.0 code. ²⁸ The parameterization of the St-LVC Hamiltonian, along all the 381 normal modes of (P,P,P) -**1** (and of (P,P,M) -**1** stereoisomer, reported in the SI), followed the standard guidelines. ^{20,21,29,30} Shortly, we considered 3 electronic states and we displaced the molecular structure along all normal coordinates using a dimensionless displacement $\Delta_\alpha = 0.02$.

The parameterization of the FrD-LVC Hamiltonian in a local picture is less straightforward, due to the fact that in our molecules, fragments are not clearly separated chemical entities, since they are the three branches of a covalent trigonal molecule. We pursued two alternative routes FrD-LVC(*i*) and FrD-LVC(*ii*) approaches, described in detail in the Supporting Information. Here in the main text we focus on the FrD-LVC(*ii*) strategy.

FrD-LVC(*ii*) approach. In both FrD-LVC(*i*) and FrD-LVC(*ii*) we defined local HOMOs and LUMOs

of the three "idealized" monomers by a inverse symmetry transformation (check Eq. 8) of respectively HOMO, HOMO-1 and HOMO-2 and of LUMO, LUMO+1, LUMO+2 orbitals of (P,P,P) -1 (see Section 5 of the Supporting Information). We then defined L_1 , L_2 and L_3 local excitations as orbital transitions between the localized orbitals (e.g. L_1 is a transition $\text{HOMO}_1 \rightarrow \text{LUMO}_1$). In this way we computed the couplings between the local excitations. We also examined possible charge-transfer states by defining states $\text{CT}(\eta \rightarrow \zeta)$, $\eta \neq \zeta$, from the orbital transition $\text{HOMO}_\eta \rightarrow \text{LUMO}_\zeta$, but they were found to lie too high in energy and not considered further (consult Section 5 of the Supporting Information).

In order to define the couplings with vibrational coordinates, in the FrD-LVC(*ii*) strategy we considered an "idealized monomer" obtained by breaking (P,P,P) -1 structure into three branches at the spiro centers, removing the bridging atoms and saturating the valences of the spiro atoms with H (Figure S1). The monomer structure was then partially optimized, by freezing all dihedral angles to the values they have in the macrocycle. Along this strategy it is then natural to use normal modes of each monomer to describe the nuclear displacements and the excited-state gradient to compute the linear $\lambda_{\eta\eta}$ parameters. On the contrary linear terms of the inter-state couplings $\lambda_{\eta\zeta}$ were neglected. It is noteworthy that due to the constrained geometry, the local transition of the idealize monomers acquire also a small intrinsic MTDM, \mathbf{m}^{int} that is computed following Jurinovic et al.³¹

The absorption (ABS) and electronic circular dichroism (ECD) spectra were computed according to the Equations in Section 2.1 of the Supporting Information, by propagating vibronic wavepackets on the coupled states of the LVC Hamiltonians. We adopted the Multi-Layer Multi-Configurational Time-Dependent Hartree^{32–35} (ML-MCTDH) method as implemented in the Quantics code³⁶ and with the setting described in the Section 2.2 of the SI. In order to reduce the computational cost we resorted to a hierarchical representation of the LVC Hamiltonian by blocks, computed according to the protocol detailed in Refs. 37,38. Such representation, first introduced in Refs. 39–41, rigorously defines a chain of coupled blocks of effective modes with the characteristics that the more blocks are included in the computation, the larger number of momenta of the full-dimensionality spectrum are exactly reproduced. Shortly, for our systems, only 24 effective modes were necessary to obtain a fully converged spectrum (i.e identical to what would have been obtained considering the contribution of all 381 normal modes) for the chosen spectral resolution (half-width at half-maximum of 0.05 eV). For FrD-LVC Hamiltonian the number of needed effective modes further reduces to 12. Additional details are given in Section 2 of SI.

4 Standard LVC Results

4.1 Adiabatic states at the Ground state geometry and JT and pJT active coordinates.

Table 1 reports the vertical energies and properties of the three lowest energy states of (P,P,P) -1 (S_1 - S_3), the only relevant ones in the spectral range of interest. The next states (S_n with $n > 3$) are dark and lie at least 0.3-0.4 eV higher in energy. Therefore, only S_1 - S_3 were considered in the parameterization of the St-LVC Hamiltonian. S_1 lies ~ 0.15 eV below S_2 and S_3 and has a small dipole strength (Dip. Str.). S_2 and S_3 are exactly degenerate (E symmetry) and much brighter than S_1 . Concerning the rotatory strength (R), S_1 has a positive R while it is negative with much lower absolute value for S_2 and S_3 . The ETDM and MTDM vectors are parallel in S_1 and anti-parallel in S_2 and S_3 . The degeneracy of S_2/S_3 indicates the existence of JT couplings, whereas the small energy gap with S_1 suggests that also pJT effects are possible.

Table 1: Symmetry, D_3 , in parenthesis those obtained considering the point group C_2 , vertical energies (VE), dipole strengths (Dip. Str., in a.u.), rotatory strengths (in the velocity gauge, R_{vel}) and angle between electric and magnetic transition dipole moments (θ_{EM}) for the three lowest energy adiabatic states of (P,P,P) -1. CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory.

System	State	Symm.	VE (eV)	Dip. Str. (a.u.)	R_{vel} (10^{-40} cgs)	θ_{EM} (degrees)
(P,P,P) -1	S_1	A ₂ (B)	3.59	2.10	3860	0
	S_2	E(B)	3.74	25.09	-2046	180.00
	S_3	E(A)	3.74	25.09	-2046	180.00

We therefore parameterized a full St-LVC Hamiltonian for these three states along all 381 ground-state normal modes of (P,P,P) -1 with Overdia code.²⁸ It is worthy of notice that the St-LVC Hamiltonian was parameterized without imposing any ansatz corresponding to a JT+pJT Hamiltonian, like the simplified model described in Section 2.2. Notwithstanding this the obtained LVC parameters very accurately adhere to such a JT+pJT scenario. In particular we identified two groups of three (quasi-)degenerate coordinates each, which carry most of the inter-state couplings among S_1 , S_2 and S_3 . They are (labels in order of increasing frequency) 337-338-339 (most contributing) and 323-324-331. These modes arise from symmetry-adapted combination of CC triple bond stretchings (337-339) and double-bond CC stretching on the spirofluorene units rise (323-324, 331), in the latter case with some additional mixing with other modes. They can be visualized through movies reported as Supporting Information.⁴² The parameters of the LVC Hamiltonian (Eqs. 3, 4) related to these modes are given in Table 2. In practice the columns λ_{ii} , and λ_{ij} in the heading of the Table report, respectively, the components along these modes of the gradients λ_{ii} (Eq. 3) and inter-state couplings λ_{ij} (Eq.4), where $i, j = 1, 2, 3$ indicate the three states S_1 , S_2 and S_3 .

Table 2 indicates that the two pairs of e modes 337-338 and 323-324 account practically for the totality of the inter-state coupling λ_{ij} , $j \neq i$ as proven by the fact that the norm of such coupling vectors along these

Table 2: St-LVC gradients λ_{ii} and interstate coupling λ_{ij} , for normal modes 337, 338, 323 and 324, their symmetry and frequency in wavenumbers for (P,P,P) -1, adopting either D_3 or C_2 point group of symmetry in the computations (C_2 irreps are given in brackets). The norm of the coupling is also shown and the total cumulative coupling involving all normal modes (CC) is provided. All λ in eV. CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory. These modes are also shown with movies as Supplementary Information.

(P,P,P) -1 (D_3 Symm)								
Mode	Symm.	Freq.(cm^{-1})	λ_{11}	λ_{22}	λ_{33}	λ_{12}	λ_{13}	λ_{23}
338	$e(b)$	2401	0	-0.004	-0.004	-0.185	0	0.133
337	$e(a)$	2401	0	0.129	-0.135	0	-0.185	0
339	$a_1(a)$	2401	-0.184	-0.184	-0.184	0	0	0
323	$e(b)$	1701	0	0	0	-0.078	0	0.055
324	$e(a)$	1701	0	0.055	-0.055	-0.001	-0.078	0
331	$a_1(a)$	1706	-0.075	-0.068	-0.068	0	0	0
Norm 6 modes			0.194	0.238	0.241	0.201	0.201	0.143
Norm all modes			0.226	0.269	0.271	0.221	0.221	0.159

few modes is always $> 85\%$ of the norm considering all modes. Similarly, the contribution of these two e pairs and their total-symmetric complementary modes, are by far the largest components along the diagonal gradients λ_{ii} .

As discussed in detail in Section 3.2 of the Supporting Information also the relative values of the different diagonal and off-diagonal elements of the Hamiltonian along these modes accurately fulfill the relations expected for a JT+pJT Hamiltonian, with small deviations attributed to occasional mixing with other modes (especially for mode 331). A recent contribution has warned about possible numerical issues in parameterizing a LVC Hamiltonian for degenerate states.²³ The fact that our diabaticization protocol provides parameters that fulfill all the expected relations from theory, although it does not impose any specific constrain on their values, supports the reliability of our approach.

Since as a matter of fact, Table 2 shows that the pair of modes 337 and 338 already represent a very significant amount of the total inter-state couplings, some insight on the characteristic shape of the adiabatic potential energy surfaces (PESs) can be obtained considering cuts along these two normal modes. Figure 1c actually reports the 2D adiabatic PES obtained by diagonalizing the LVC Hamiltonian along modes 337 and 338 for (P,P,P) -1. It is possible to recognize the symmetry-imposed CoI between S_2 and S_3 , due to the JT coupling. Very interestingly both S_1 and S_2 show three symmetric minima, reminiscent of the three minima of the local states (see SI for contour plots). A detailed analysis in Section 3.3.3 in the SI also shows that these minima are due to the pJT couplings. In fact, setting the latter couplings to zero the S_2/S_3 CoI gets the typical JT mexican-hat shape, whereas S_1 exhibits a minimum in D_3 symmetry. On the contrary, setting to zero the JT couplings, the two surfaces S_2 and S_3 touch each other in D_3 symmetry where they both have a minimum, whereas S_1 shows a transition state in D_3 and it assumes the shape of a mexican hat (Figures S13-S14).

5 ABS and ECD vibronic spectra predicted by the delocalized St-LVC model

The computed ABS and ECD LVC spectra for (P,P,P) -1 are compared to experimentally measured spectra in Figure 2, showing a very good agreement. St-LVC spectra reproduce all the spectral bands and shoulders with correct relative intensities. The impact of inter-state couplings can be appreciated by recomputing the ABS and ECD spectra setting such couplings to zero, so that the LVC model collapses into a simple adiabatic model named FC|VG.⁴³ Although FC|VG model correctly predicts the main sign of the ECD spectrum,¹¹ Figure 2 shows that its agreement with the measured spectrum is much poorer, thus documenting the remarkable effect played by nonadiabatic couplings. It is therefore interesting to dissect the role of the different coupling mechanisms.

Figure 2: a) Comparison of experimentally measured (acetonitrile) and computed (in vacuo) ABS (top) and ECD (bottom) spectra of (P,P,P) -1. Effect of the different Jahn-Teller (λ_{23}), pseudo-Jahn-Teller ($\lambda_{12}, \lambda_{13}$) coupling are investigated setting them selectively to zero, whereas FC|VG represents the case in which they are all simultaneously set to zero. b) St-LVC (solid) and FC|VG (dotted) ABS and ECD spectra of (P,P,P) -1, showing also the contribution of individual spectra. Notice that for St-LVC, the individual spectrum for a given state represents the contribution of the corresponding autocorrelation function. S_2 and S_3 are degenerate and their spectra fully overlap, therefore they are shown together. 4 hierarchy blocks, corresponding to 24 effective coordinates were used. CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) LVC parameterization. All calculated spectra were redshifted by 0.105 eV, and all stick transitions were convoluted with a Gaussian of HWHM = 0.05 eV. Computed ABS intensities were multiplied by a factor 0.41 (ABS) and 0.26 (ECD).

In order to selectively investigate the relative role of the JT couplings (λ_{23}) between S_2 and S_3 and the pJT couplings between S_1 with the degenerate pair S_2/S_3 (λ_{12} and λ_{13}) they were alternatively set to zero. Figure 2 shows that JT S_2 - S_3 $E \otimes e$ coupling barely affects the spectral shapes. On the contrary, pJT couplings have a drastic impact on the spectra and constitute, therefore, the most important nonadiabatic effect for these systems. As discussed above, switching off both JT and pJT couplings we get the FC|VG limit.

For a more detailed analysis, we plot the individual contributions (i.e. those coming from the auto-correlation functions) of states S_1 , S_2 , and S_3 to the LVC and FC|VG spectra.⁴⁴ Switching off the inter-state couplings, each of these contributions collapses into the FC|VG spectrum of the corresponding state.

For ABS, the LVC contributions due to photoexcitation to S_2 or S_3 have an identical spectral shape with a significant contribution in the energy region of the S_1 state. Such low-energy bands are missing in FC|VG calculations since the intrinsic contribution of S_1 absorption is totally negligible as shown in Table 1. The ECD spectra arises from a much stronger contribution from S_1 than from S_2 and S_3 . On the balance, it appears that the ECD bands at 3.3 eV and 3.6 eV arise from the combined mutual cancellations of the contributions of the three states, and the intensity ratio observed in the experiment depends on a subtle equilibrium of many factors, like the inter-state coupling, the energy gap between states, and the norm and orientation of the transition dipoles. Remarkably the LVC lowest-energy bands do not fall at the same energy for ABS and ECD but well below the position of the 0-0 band of the S_1 state. This fact indicates that not only there is a transfer of intensity toward S_1 (at least for ABS) but, additionally, the S_1 vibrational states remarkably mix with S_2 and S_3 ones, creating new mixed vibronic states at lower energies.

Our quantum dynamical computations give also access to the time evolution of the electronic populations after an initial photoexcitation to S_1 , S_2 , or S_3 delocalized states. They are analyzed in Figure 3 to complement our analysis on the relevance of the inter-state coupling on the optical properties. The photodynamics is extremely fast with population transfers occurring in the first ~ 20 fs followed by a number of quantum beats by ± 0.1 . Interestingly, according to our model, independently of the initially excited state, S_1 becomes the most populated state in very short times (~ 10 fs). This finding is in line with the observation of a large transfer of intensity to the low-energy region of the spectra.

Before concluding this section it is important to remark that our approach can simulate equally well the ECD of the stereoisomer (P,P,M) -1 (Figure S22). In fact it is less symmetric and belongs to C_2 symmetry and therefore it is not, strictly speaking a JT+pJT system, and it does not feature Conical Intersection imposed by symmetry. Very interestingly, in agreement with experiments, our computations predict that the ECD of (P,P,M) -1 and (P,P,P) -1 are very similar, despite significant differences in the rotatory strengths

Figure 3: Population dynamics of the diabatic states for (P,P,P) -1. Initial photoexcitation on S_1 (left), S_2 (central) and S_3 (right). Computation with 24 effective vibrational models corresponding to 4 hierarchical blocks. St-LVC model parameterized with CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d).

of the individual states. This finding further documents that only a full non-adiabatic multi-state vibronic approach can provide a robust description of the optical properties of these species. For the sake of brevity the results for (P,P,M) -1 are reported and discussed in detail in Section 6 of the Supporting Information

5.1 Assignment of Bands with Reduced Dimensionality Models

In order to assign the individual vibronic peaks of the ABS and ECD spectra to excitations of specific states and specific modes it is expedient to resort to a time-independent (TI) approach, where vibronic eigenstates are obtained by explicit diagonalization of the LVC Hamiltonian. Unfortunately, this computational approach is practical only for a very reduced set of coordinates. Figure 4 shows a comparison of ABS and ECD spectra computed with the full dimensionality model (reproduced with the 24 effective coordinates), and with reduced models including only the triplet of modes at $\sim 2400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (3Q, modes 337-339), or two triplets of modes (6Q), i.e. also the triplet 323-324, 331 at $\sim 1700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, i.e. those with the largest gradients and couplings reported in Table 2. The main features of the spectra are already nicely reproduced with the 3Q model, whereas the 6Q model further improves the quality of the spectra providing results in semi-quantitative agreement with the full-dimensionality computation. We conclude that it is possible to gain insight on the characteristics of the nature of the vibronic states responsible for the main peaks even considering the simple 3Q model. Figure 4 shows the most intense stick transitions from $|g; \mathbf{0}\rangle$, the ground vibrational state ($|\mathbf{0}\rangle$) of the ground electronic state $|g\rangle$ to the vibronic eigenstates arising from the coupling of the three states S_1 - S_3 .

They are combinations of diabatic vibronic states and are named $|\alpha\rangle$, with labels $\alpha=0,1,2\dots$ in order of increasing frequency. In Table 3 states $|\alpha\rangle$ are assigned in terms of their main components $S_i(337^k338^l339^m)$ where $i = 1,2,3$ and k, l and m are the quantum numbers of modes 337 ($e(b)$), 338 ($e(a)$) and 339 (a_1), respectively. To complete the previous notation we specify that a mode is omitted if its quantum number is 0, and that the ground vibrational state of each of the three diabatic states is simply indicated by $\mathbf{0}$, i.e. $S_1(\mathbf{0})$, $S_2(\mathbf{0})$ and $S_3(\mathbf{0})$.

The first strong ABS band at ~ 3.3 eV is due to transitions to a pair of degenerate vibronic states, **1, 2**, which mainly arise from the mixing of the ground state of the bright S_3 ($S_3(\mathbf{0})$) or S_2 ($S_2(\mathbf{0})$), and respectively the vibronic state on S_1 with one quantum on either mode 337 ($S_1(337^1)$), or 338 ($S_1(338^1)$), as imposed by symmetry.

Notice that any combination of this degenerate pair of vibronic states is still an eigenstate and therefore their assignment should be considered collectively. Next ABS peak, at ~ 3.6 eV, is mainly due to transitions to a second pair of states **7, 8**, dominated by the same vibronic components found in **1, 2** but with the addition of a quantum on mode 338. In particular, state **7** is mainly described by the combination band $S_1(337^1,338^1)$ plus the fundamental $S_3(338^1)$, whereas for state **8** the main component is the overtone $S_1(338^2)$ and the fundamental $S_2(338^1)$. Both states do also show a $\sim 16\%$ component corresponding to the ground vibrational state of one component of the E pair (either $S_3(\mathbf{0})$ or $S_2(\mathbf{0})$). The third peak at ~ 3.9 eV has many contributions, the largest being due to the pair of states **23, 24**. These states are a vibronic progression of states **7, 8**, meaning that their main components are obtained from those of states **7, 8** with an additional quantum along the total-symmetric mode 339.

Moving to ECD, the lowest band at ~ 3.25 eV, is due to the transition to the lowest vibronic state $\mathbf{0}$, which mainly corresponds to the ground vibrational state of S_1 , $S_1(\mathbf{0})$. It is interesting to notice that such state carries a strong and positive ECD, whereas it is very weak in ABS (this result is a direct consequence of the dipole and rotatory strengths of S_1). The first negative band at ~ 3.4 eV is originated on the contrary by transitions to the degenerate vibronic states **1, 2** and the second negative band at ~ 3.65 eV arises from the balance of many positive and negative contributions. The most important ones are due to transitions to states **7, 8** (see Table 3).

5.1.1 Alternative assignments with a localized model obtained by symmetry transformation of the St-LVC Hamiltonian

Exploiting the considerations in Section 2.2, for (P,P,P) -1 it is possible to obtain a 3Q localized model formally equivalent to the delocalized model discussed in the previous section by applying a simple symmetry

transformation. The parameters of this equivalent localized model are reported in Section 3.2 and in Table S6 in the Supporting Information. The spectra computed with this model shall be identical by construction (and they are within the numerical accuracy). However, they provide an alternative assignment of the main bands in terms of localized electronic states on the three branches of the microcycle (L_1 - L_3), and excitations of the corresponding local vibrational modes (q_1 - q_3). They are reported in Table 3. In this localized picture the first lowest peaks, giving rise to the positive/negative doublet in ECD have a very simple interpretation. In fact they do arise from the different symmetry-adapted combinations of the ground vibrational states of the three local states, $L_1(\mathbf{0})$, $L_2(\mathbf{0})$ and $L_3(\mathbf{0})$. More specifically the eigenstate $\mathbf{0}$, lying at 3.19 eV, is the total-symmetric combination of such states. This local picture provides a quite intuitive understanding of why this band is weak in absorption and strong in ECD. In fact, it is weak in ABS because the three local transition dipoles are mainly confined in the approximate molecular plane xy and, their components in such plane cancel out like three vectors with identical module forming an equilateral triangle (see Figure 1 and Table S3 in the SI). For ECD, the small ETDM are compensated by a very large MTDM. In fact, the MTDMs of all local states are aligned to the C_3 axis, i.e. the direction perpendicular to the approximate molecular plane (z axis, see Figure 1 and Table S3 in the SI) and they all add, resulting in a very large value. The first negative peak is due to the pair of degenerate states $\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{2}$ at ~ 3.28 eV, which correspond in this localized picture to the two E -symmetry combinations of the same vibronic states $L_1(\mathbf{0})$, $L_2(\mathbf{0})$ and $L_3(\mathbf{0})$. In this case they are strong both in ABS and in ECD (negative) because of the combination of signs of the different contributions. The higher energy bands are due to states in which the local vibrations are excited. However, the fact that neither the electronic states or the vibrational states have a well defined symmetry makes their interpretation not straightforward.

Table 3: Index in increasing order energy, energy (in eV), dipole strength (in a.u.), rotatory strength (in 10^{-40} cgs) and assignment of main vibronic states contributing to the ABS and ECD spectral bands of P,P,P -**1** for the model 3Q (three coordinates). Up to three transitions with the largest weights are reported. The energies were redshifted by 0.255 eV for better correspondence with Figure 4 sticks. The assignment of bands 23 and 24 is very complex in the localized picture and is not reported.

Index	Energy	Dip. Str.	Rot. Str.	Assignment	
				Delocalized	Localized
0	3.19	1.41	2630	$S_1(\mathbf{0})$	$L_1(0)+L_2(0)+L_3(0)$
1	3.28	11.46	-946	$S_1(337^1)+S_3(\mathbf{0})$	$-L_2(0)+L_3(0)$
2	3.28	11.46	-946	$S_1(338^1)+S_2(\mathbf{0})$	$-L_1(0)+L_2(0)+L_3(0)$
7	3.57	5.76	-475	$S_1(337^1,338^1)+S_3(\mathbf{0})+S_3(338^1)$	$L_1(q_1^1)-L_1(q_3^1)-L_2(q_1^1)+L_2(q_3^1)$
8	3.57	5.76	-475	$-S_1(338^2)+S_2(\mathbf{0})-S_2(338^1)$	$L_1(q_2^1)-L_1(q_3^1)-L_3(q_2^1)+L_3(q_3^1)$
23	3.86	1.11	-92	$S_1(337^1,338^1,339^1)+S_3(339^1)+S_3(338^1,339^1)$	-
24	3.86	1.11	-92	$S_1(338^2,339^1)-S_2(339^1)+S_2(338^1,339^1)$	-

Figure 4: Comparison of St-LVC spectra of (P,P,P) -DES3 computed by accounting for the effect of all 381 normal coordinates, like in previous figures (through a hierarchy with 24 effective modes), with those obtained with simple models including the three (3Q) or the six (6Q) normal coordinates with largest gradients and interstate couplings. The stick transitions for the 3Q model are also shown. For consistency with previous results, all calculated spectra were redshifted by 0.105 eV (the convoluted and stick spectra obtained with reduced models and sticks were redshifted by 0.255 eV) and scaled by 0.41 (ABS) and 0.26 (ECD) for the full model. Spectra with reduced-dimensionality models have the same total intensity (the integral in the frequency domain) of the spectra in full dimensionality. However for a better comparison they were scaled to match the intensity of the lowest-energy peak. All stick transitions were convoluted with a Gaussian of $\text{HWHM} = 0.05$ eV (0.09 eV for reduced models)

6 ABS and ECD vibronic spectra predicted by a localized exciton-like FrD-LVC model

In this section we recompute the ABS and ECD spectra from scratch by a localized exciton-like model obtained through an independent parameterization of an FrD-LVC Hamiltonian with the code Overdia.²⁸ As

we noticed in the Introduction, such an alternative excitonic-like theoretical approach is directly allied with the idea inspiring the design of these compounds, i.e. locking in a chiral arrangement identical chromophores so that their interaction triggers a chiroptical response. It should be therefore remarked that the calculations discussed here are profoundly different from what presented in Section 5.3.1, where we just made a symmetry transformation of the 3Q St-LVC Hamiltonian (a strategy not applicable to the full-dimensionality models), obtaining results equivalent by definition, with the sole scope to explore an alternative assignment of the same computed stick bands.

We report here only the results of the FrD-LVC(*ii*) strategy. ABS and ECD spectra computed with the FrD-LVC(*i*) show some remarkable differences from the experimental ones and those obtained with St-LVC. They are shown in SI and we attribute these discrepancies mainly to the fact that the local excitations are not simply HOMO-LUMO transitions, and more orbitals are involved. Despite these differences, model FrD-LVC(*i*) provides two interesting information: (i) the 6 CT states corresponding to the displacement of an electron from the HOMO of a monomer to the LUMO of a different one lie very high in energy and are very weakly coupled to local states (< 0.035 eV); therefore they do not need to be considered further. (ii) The predicted exciton coupling is -0.059 eV, a value extremely similar to the one obtained by symmetry considerations as $1/3$ of the energy gap of the adiabatic states at the reference geometry (i.e. using Eq. 9, $\beta \sim -0.05$ eV). Such an estimate of the coupling therefore appears to be very robust, and consequently it can be used also for strategy FrD-LVC(*ii*).

In order to apply FrD-LVC(*ii*) strategy we perform computations on the idealized monomer defined in the computational section. The vertical transition energy computed with TD-DFT for the bright state of such monomer is 3.72 eV, very close to what estimated on the grounds of symmetry considerations from the energies of the three lowest adiabatic states of (P,P,P) -**1**, i.e. 3.69 eV (Eq. 9). Interestingly such localized transition is mainly (84 %) a HOMO \rightarrow LUMO excitation, and the orbitals of the monomer closely resemble those obtained by combining those of (P,P,P) -**1** with an inverse symmetry rotation, see Figures S18-S19 in the SI. On the other hand, the existence of additional contributions (16%) confirms that the idealized definition of the localized states adopted according to strategy (i) was only approximate. The localized vibrations most important for the spectra (those most displaced) are discussed in Section 5.2.2. in the Supporting Information. They are the CC triple bond stretching and CC double bond stretching, and the parameters are in perfect agreement with what expected from what observed for the St-LVC Hamiltonian (Table 2) on the grounds of the simple model in Section 2.3.

Data in Table S8 of the Supporting Information report the ETDM, and the MTDM that the local excitation of each monomer acquires in the (P,P,P) -**1** excitonic system. As anticipated, although the monomers

are achiral in a fully relaxed geometry, they do have a slightly axially chiral conformation in (P,P,P) -**1** and therefore they possess an intrinsic MTDM, which is however very small in comparison to the excitonic contribution, thus having only a slight impact on the ECD spectrum.

Finally, Figure 5 compares the ABS and ECD spectra obtained with the full dimensionality St-LVC and FrD-LVC(ii) Hamiltonians, showing that they are both in very nice agreement with experiment. The similarity of these results provides a conclusive evidence of the qualitative equivalence of two delocalized, JT-like or localized excitonic-like pictures proving that they can both explain the (chiro-)optical properties of (P,P,P) -**1**. This similarity also supports the robustness of the independent protocols adopted to obtain the parameters for both St-LVC and FrD-LVC(ii) Hamiltonians. Going in deeper detail, the FrD-LVC(ii) results show some moderately larger discrepancies, a finding that is not surprising, due to the intrinsic approximations necessary to define the "idealized monomer" and to parameterize the model.

7 Conclusions

We have developed a unified theoretical framework to describe the chiroptical properties of symmetric cyclic π -conjugated systems, from both the point of view of exciton coupling and of non-adiabatic approaches based on Jahn–Teller (JT) and pseudo-JT effects, two families of models that have been traditionally considered separated. By constructing linear vibronic coupling (LVC) Hamiltonians in both localized and delocalized representations, we demonstrate that they can both reproduce the experimental ECD spectra of the D_3 -symmetric spirobifluorene macrocycle (P,P,P) -**1**, but we document that in both cases it is mandatory the explicit inclusion of couplings between nuclear and electronic motions. This comparison reveals the dominant role of JT and pseudo-JT couplings and highlights the essential influence of symmetry-imposed conical intersections, exciton–charge transfer interactions, and the constructive or destructive combination of local transition dipoles. Importantly, the same methodology also captures the optical response of a less symmetric C_2 stereoisomer (P,P,M) -**1**, underscoring the robustness and generality of the approach.

This dual-framework strategy not only bridges the conceptual gap between excitonic and vibronic pictures but also provides mechanistic insight into how symmetry and electronic structure shape chiroptical responses. By showing that non-adiabatic couplings are essential even within excitonic interpretations, this work offers a valuable design principle for tailoring the optical activity of advanced chiral systems. The framework presented here lays the groundwork for predictive modelling of next generation chiroptical materials in molecular photonics, optoelectronics, and spintronic applications.

Figure 5: Comparison of experimental (thicker gray lines) and calculated (solid lines) nonadiabatic ABS (top) and ECD (bottom) spectra of (P,P,P) -**1** computed within the delocalized (red) and localized (blue) pictures. All spectra were redshifted by 0.105 eV and scaled by 0.41 (ABS) and 0.26 (ECD). Fully-converged spectra, obtained with reduced dimensionality models accounting for 4 hierarchy blocks, i.e. 24 effective coordinates for (St-LVC) and 12 for (FrD-LVC). CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) diabatization.

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Supporting Information

A more extended derivation of the simple 3-states 3-modes model, additional computational details; plots of the 3D PES for different limiting cases; Computations on the stereoisomer PPM. Movies of the most important normal modes. Further data and namely the LVC input files are available at the Zenodo database under the accession code <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16603255>.⁴⁵

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- (44) While such a decomposition is formally exact for FC|VG, the total spectrum is their sum, (for more information check the theory section). On the other hand, the LVC spectrum arises from both auto- and cross-correlation terms, however, Figure S16 in the SI shows that the cross-correlation terms have a negligible impact, therefore also the LVC spectrum can be split into the contribution of three terms, one for each initial state.
- (45) Aranda, D.; Alonso, J. L.; Santoro, F. Jahn-Teller Couplings and Exciton Models Reveal Origins of Chiroptical Activity in Symmetric Cyclic π -Conjugated Systems. 2025; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16603256>.

Graphical TOC Entry

